

Research Proposal Letter

To Susan, Huff

President, Healthcare Congress Alliance

1100 Johnson Ferry road, Suite 300

Atlanta, GA 30342

Dear Ms. Huff,

Constant interventions and reforms have been the reason for quality healthcare and reduced death rates; however there is much need in understanding the altering requirements of inmates. According to Conroy a research analyst the healthcare system for inmates is failing drastically to meet the required principles mostly based on lack to proper procedures and experienced nursing staff available. The inmate population is constantly rising and nurtures care is not readily available, and there is an obvious element missing from the healthcare system that requires nursing as a specialist role. There is also a lack of suitable procedures and in most cases the nurtures are held accountable. Based on an interview conducted from various inmates, my interview experience with Austin an elderly inmate of Georgia State Penitentiary faced severe liver dysfunctionality and was refused any proper healthcare initially which caused his liver excessive damage and after 2 weeks of suffering he was finally shifted to a hospital but the damage was done.

The biggest problem our healthcare system is facing is presenting the patients to the nurseries as the last resort, which considerably reduces the effectiveness nursing can actually have, the management needs to start focusing on providing nursing at the very beginning in order to ensure each inmate receives excellent healthcare. As the President of the Healthcare Congress alliance you must be considerably aware of this growing concern, which needs to be dealt with at the soonest to ensure every living person receives quality healthcare. My purpose in writing to you is to highlight some of the effective procedures that can be implemented in order to reduce healthcare issues drastically, multifaceted quality improvement intervention models need to be implemented.

The theoretical framework that I suggest in order to improve the healthcare for inmates involves organizational changes and specifying clinical guidelines for diseases. In order to bring about organizational changes it is necessary to secure a continuity of nursing support from the beginning instead of at the end, for this purpose small organizational changes need to be sought, which also includes increasing the nursing staff for inmates. According to Boswell, there is much need on providing nursing care for inmates, since in most detention centers the detention officer is responsible for providing medications, who lack the necessary qualifications to deal with an unforeseen event in many situations inmates are taken to hospitals for conditions that a nurse can resolve in minutes. If left unresolved there is a likely chance that inmates might develop severer diseases.

Another possible intervention could be the formation of a quality improvement team who would be responsible for conducted regular visits to the institute, monitoring key patients and identifying high risk illnesses. They would also specify the likely course of action during any emergency, the quality improvement team will be responsible for assessing the possible threats

patients possess they can also ensure the institute is properly equipped for the treatment along with ensuring the nursing staff has enough knowledge to deal with such a situation. The whole system can be drastically altered by simply changing the organizational design and incorporating nursing staffs throughout the diagnosis of a disease till the cure, which will drastically help improve the brittle health care conditions.

Many countries are facing financial constraints in terms of healthcare, the design suggested is cost effective, the Southern health care partners trust is a possible funding source if needed, based on their commitment to providing excellent inmate health care services. The reason why I sent you this letter is because just like me your aim is to improve the healthcare system for every living person as evident from your 30 years of serving the HCEA. Please support my vision in order to ensure the wellbeing of everybody.

Sincerely,

*Student's Name*

Student's Name

Works Cited

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